

Correction to: Psychosocial factors associated with quality of life in cancer survivors: umbrella review

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In this article, the author's name Iris van der Heide was incorrectly written as Iris van der Heijden.

In addition, the affiliation details for Cinzia Brunelli were incorrectly given as 'Dipartimento Di Scienze Cliniche E Di Comunità, Università Degli Studi Di Milano, Milan, Italy' but should have been 'Scientific Directorate, Fondazione Istituto Di Ricovero E Cura a Carattere Scientifico, Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale Dei Tumori, Milan, Italy'.

The original article has been corrected.

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Extended author information available on the last page of the article

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